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Monitoring of Cement Hydration using Terahertz Radiation

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Application of cement

▲ Building structure

- Cement mainly used for building structure material, as its high efficiency and strength.

▲ Floor finish, road pavement

Cement hydration

✘ Cement hydration reaction

▲ Cement curing process

- Curing is a process that maintaining appropriate moisture and temperature conditions.
- Curing proceed cement hydration process, which forms C-S-H gel that makes proper bonding with aggregates enhancing the mechanical properties.

Mechanical properties increase with curing time

▲ Strength change with curing time

Issue of cement deterioration

▲ Non-uniformity due to difference in hydration

▲ Deterioration of cement

- Insufficient and non-uniform hydration causes deterioration of cement.
- An evaluation method is needed to evaluate the curing process of cement.

Terahertz

- Terahertz is an electromagnetic wave having a frequency of 0.1 THz to 30 THz.
- It has an intermediate nature of radio waves and light waves, so it can penetrate nonmetallic materials and has straightness in the air.
- It has the advantages of being able to test without the need for a medium, and having high spatial resolution enabling more detailed inspection.

Terahertz radiation

▲ Schematic of terahertz system

▲ Monitoring of cement hydration

- Analysis of structure and composition changes by cement hydration reaction and correlation with terahertz radiation.

Conclusion

- 3PB test was conducted to validate the change of flexural modulus according to the degree of hydration of cement.
- FFT and extinction coefficient were calculated to analyze the THz waveform according to the hydration reaction.
- FT-IR and SEM analysis confirmed the chemical and structural changes due to the hydration reaction of the cement, which confirmed that the THz waves were changed.

